

THE DETERMINISTIC AND STOCHASTIC ENERGY-BASED CHARACTERIZATION OF COMPOSITES - A GENERALIZED THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK -

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SUMMARY

This paper presents a generalized theoretical framework for an energy-based characterization of composite materials. The generalized framework allows the formulation of both the deterministic and stochastic energy-based characterization techniques, enabling the identification of similarities and differences of the two techniques as well as their direct comparison. Comparative analyses show that both the techniques work similarly when the prior variances for the stochastic technique is high. However the stochastic technique has been found to outperform when appropriate prior knowledge is provided and has shown successful identification of elastic constants.

Keywords: Energy-based characterization, composites, deterministic and stochastic identification, Kalman filter, pseudo-inverse

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials can be tailored to possess various high-performance properties such as high stiffness, high strength and low density and have seen increasing applications in fields which require severe design criteria [1]. Despite the popularity, the behavior of these materials is however complicated and often unpredictable due to the anisotropic properties inevitably introduced to meet the criteria. This has given rise to the need for the reliable characterization of anisotropic materials, which essentially requires the identification of elastic constants as the primary challenge [2-4].

While the dominantly used orthogonal testing approach identifies elastic constants using uniaxial tests each conducted to determine the stress-strain relation along one of the orthogonal axes fixed to the specimen [5], the approach which received recent attention characterizes materials by evaluating a specimen on a continuum basis via full-field and/or surface measurements. Lecompte et al. [6-8] identified the elastic constants of a perforated cruciform specimen by minimizing the residuals between the measured and the computed full-field strain data. Grediac et al. [9-11] developed a technique that identifies elastic constants by applying the principle of virtual work, substituting full-field/surface measurements, finding virtual fields and inversely solving for the elastic constants.

The authors [12-14] developed the so-called energy-based characterization, which is built upon the principle of total potential energy and identifies elastic constants by equating the external work derived from the surface displacement/force measurements with the strain energy derived from the full-field strain measurement. For the identification of elastic constants, two numerical techniques, a deterministic technique that uses pseudo-inverse and a stochastic technique that uses Kalman filter were proposed. Unlike others, these techniques can update the elastic constants at every acquisition of measurements by utilizing all the measurements collected to date, and this allows the techniques to identify more reliable elastic constants. Despite the advantages, the techniques have been independently developed, and similarities and differences in formulation and performance have not been investigated.

This paper presents a generalized theoretical framework for the deterministic and stochastic energy-based characterization. While the deterministic technique only utilizes direct measurements, the stochastic technique handles prior knowledge and measurements probabilistically and recursively updates the estimation. The generalized theoretical framework identifies such differences as well as similarities in formulation and can be further used to implement both the techniques in one platform and make a direct comparison.

The paper is organized as follows. The next section presents the theoretical framework of the energy-based characterization. Deterministic and Stochastic techniques are then formulated in Section 3. Section 4 investigates the effectiveness of the deterministic and stochastic techniques comparatively and for the identification of elastic constants, and conclusions are summarized in the final section.

THE ENERGY-BASED CHARACTERIZATION

Stress-strain Constitutive Relationships

The energy-based characterization commences with the representation of stress-strain constitutive relationships in terms of the elastic constants. As one of the most popularly used anisotropic materials, consider symmetric angle-ply laminate, which consists of two types of lamina, each with a fiber orientation of $\pm\theta$. The unidirectional lamina defines the material coordinate system $\{M\}$ and relates stresses and strains in the elastic regime as

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_{12} \end{bmatrix} \text{ or } \{M\}\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \{M\}\mathbf{Q}\{M\}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

where $\{M\}\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\{M\}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ are the stress and the strain vectors and $\{M\}\mathbf{Q}$ is the matrix containing elastic constants to identify. The rest of the paper denotes the set of elastic constants in the vector form as $\{M\}\mathbf{q}$.

Given the stress-strain relations of lamina in the material coordinate system, the stress-strain relations of the symmetric angle-ply laminate with a fiber orientation of $\pm\theta$ can

be described with $\{M\}\mathbf{q}$ in the global coordinate system $\{G\}$ aligned to the material principle axes as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \sigma_y \\ \sigma_s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{Q}_{xx}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \{M\}\mathbf{q}) & \mathcal{Q}_{xy}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \{M\}\mathbf{q}) & \mathcal{Q}_{xs}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \{M\}\mathbf{q}) \\ \mathcal{Q}_{xy}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \{M\}\mathbf{q}) & \mathcal{Q}_{yy}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \{M\}\mathbf{q}) & \mathcal{Q}_{ys}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \{M\}\mathbf{q}) \\ \mathcal{Q}_{xs}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \{M\}\mathbf{q}) & \mathcal{Q}_{ys}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \{M\}\mathbf{q}) & \mathcal{Q}_{ss}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \{M\}\mathbf{q}) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \varepsilon_y \\ \varepsilon_s \end{bmatrix} \text{ or } \{G\}\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \{G\}\mathbf{Q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \{M\}\mathbf{q})\{G\}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

where the components of the constitutive matrix $\{G\}\mathbf{Q}(\cdot)$ given in the Voigt notation, $\{G\}\mathbf{q} = [\mathcal{Q}_{xx}(\cdot), \mathcal{Q}_{yy}(\cdot), \mathcal{Q}_{ss}(\cdot), \mathcal{Q}_{xy}(\cdot), \mathcal{Q}_{xs}(\cdot), \mathcal{Q}_{ys}(\cdot)]^T$, are linearly related to those in the material coordinates system in terms of the transformation matrix $\{M\}\mathbf{H}(\boldsymbol{\theta})$ as

$$\{G\}\mathbf{q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \{M\}\mathbf{q}) = \{M\}\mathbf{H}(\boldsymbol{\theta})\{M\}\mathbf{q} \quad (2)$$

The subsequent sections treat variables and parameters mostly in the global coordinate system. We will adopt the linear constitutive equation (1) in the following form:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{Q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}; \mathbf{q}_M)\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (3)$$

by dropping the notation of the global coordinate system $\{G\}$ and subscripting the material coordinate system $\{M\}$ as M .

Energy-based Characterization

Assuming that the energy discrepancy is not caused by anything other than the external work, the variation of the potential energy of the test specimen, Φ , is expressed in terms of the variations of the strain energy U and the external work W as

$$\Delta\Phi = \Delta U - \Delta W \quad (4)$$

This further introduces potential energy of the test specimen in the variation of the variational form:

$$\delta\Delta\Phi = \delta\Delta U - \delta\Delta W \quad (5)$$

where the strain energy term in the elastic deformation of the planar specimen with volume V , or thickness t and area A , is

$$\delta\Delta U = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^T \mathbf{Q}(\boldsymbol{\theta}, \mathbf{q}_M) \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} dV = \left\{ \frac{1}{2} t \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 \int_A \Delta\varepsilon_i \Delta\varepsilon_j dA \mathbf{h}_{ij}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \right\} \mathbf{q}_M \quad (6)$$

whilst the external work term created by the loading on the surface S is given by

$$\delta\Delta W = \frac{1}{2} \int_S \Delta\mathbf{u}^T \Delta\mathbf{f} dS \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{f} are the displacement and force vectors, respectively.

The energy-based characterization is based on the principle of minimum potential energy and further assumes that the external work is fully converted into the strain energy:

$$\delta\Delta U = \delta\Delta W \quad (8)$$

Given the K times deformation, the substitution of Equation (6) into Equation (8) results in a set of linear equations:

$$\mathbf{g}(\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^k; \boldsymbol{\theta})^T \mathbf{q}_M = \delta\Delta W^k, \forall k \in \{1, \dots, K\} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{g}(\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^k; \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \left\{ \frac{1}{2} t \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 \int_A \Delta\varepsilon_i^k \Delta\varepsilon_j^k dA \mathbf{h}_{ij}(\boldsymbol{\theta}) \right\}.$$

When the material tests are performed, we will receive the measured values of $\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^k$ and $\delta\Delta W^k$, i.e., \mathbf{z}_ε^k and \mathbf{z}_W^k . The energy-based characterization utilizes the measurements and the linear equations to solve for the elastic constants \mathbf{q}_M .

NUMERICAL TECHNIQUES FOR ENERGY-BASED CHARACTERIZATION

Deterministic Technique

The deterministic technique does not consider the effect of measurement errors and treat measurements of the full-field strain and the external work as true values:

$$\mathbf{z}_\varepsilon^k \approx \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^k, \quad \mathbf{z}_W^k \approx \delta\Delta W^k \quad (11)$$

The substitution of Eq. (3) into Eq. (2) and the assembly of the linear equations for measurements 1 to K yield a set of simultaneous algebraic equations:

$$\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{z}_\varepsilon^{1:K}; \boldsymbol{\theta}) \mathbf{q}_M = \mathbf{z}_W^{1:K} \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{G}(\cdot)$ is a matrix assembling all $\mathbf{g}(\cdot)$. The material parameters can be thus identified as

$$\mathbf{q}_M = \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{z}_\varepsilon^{1:K}; \boldsymbol{\theta})^+ \mathbf{z}_W^{1:K} \quad (13)$$

where $(\cdot)^+$ is a pseudoinverse of (\cdot) .

Stochastic Technique

The stochastic technique considers measurement errors \mathbf{v}_ε^k and v_W^k :

$$\mathbf{z}_\varepsilon^k = \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^k + \mathbf{v}_\varepsilon^k \quad (14a)$$

$$\mathbf{z}_W^k = \delta\Delta W^k + v_W^k \quad (14b)$$

In a simple approach, Eq. (14a) can be implicitly embedded in the assumption:

$$\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{z}_\varepsilon^k; \boldsymbol{\theta}) = \mathbf{g}(\Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^k; \boldsymbol{\theta}) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{v}_\varepsilon^k; \boldsymbol{\theta}) \quad (15)$$

This writes a measurement equation as

$$z_W^k = \left\{ \mathbf{g}(\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^k; \boldsymbol{\theta}) - \mathbf{g}(\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^k; \boldsymbol{\theta}) \right\}^T \mathbf{q}_M + v_W^k \quad (16)$$

The reformulation of Kalman filter consequently estimates the parameter set $\mathbf{q}_M^{k|k}$ and its covariance $\mathbf{P}^{k|k}$ from measurements and prior knowledge, $\mathbf{q}_M^{k|k-1}$ and $\mathbf{P}^{k|k-1}$, as

$$\mathbf{q}_M^{k|k} = \mathbf{q}_M^{k|k-1} + \mathbf{K}^k \left(z_W^k - \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{z}_\varepsilon^k; \boldsymbol{\theta})^T \mathbf{q}_M^{k|k-1} \right), \quad \mathbf{P}^{k|k} = \mathbf{P}^{k|k-1} - \mathbf{K}^k \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{z}_\varepsilon^k; \boldsymbol{\theta})^T \mathbf{P}^{k|k-1} \quad (17)$$

where Kalman Gain \mathbf{K}^k is given by

$$\mathbf{K}^k = \mathbf{P}^{k|k-1T} \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{z}_\varepsilon^k; \boldsymbol{\theta}) \left\{ \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{z}_\varepsilon^k; \boldsymbol{\theta})^T \mathbf{P}^{k|k-1} \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{z}_\varepsilon^k; \boldsymbol{\theta}) + P_W^k + \sum_{i=1}^4 (q_M^{k|k-1})_i^2 (P_g^k)_i \right\}^{-1} \quad (18)$$

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Concept Proving by Algebraic Problem

The problem made in this section consists of the following two sets of equations:

$$\mathbf{z}_g^k = \mathbf{g}^k + \mathbf{v}_g^k, \quad z_W^k = \mathbf{g}^{kT} + v_W^k = (\mathbf{z}_g^k - \mathbf{v}_g^k)^T \mathbf{q} + v_W^k, \quad \forall k \in \{1, \dots, K\} \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{q} = [q_1, q_2]^T$ are the constants to estimate, and $\mathbf{g}^k = [g_1^k, g_2^k]^T$ are the true multipliers, which to resemble $\mathbf{g}(\Delta \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^k; \boldsymbol{\theta})$ take a variety of values according to

$$g_i^k = \mu_i^k (g_i^{\max} - g_i^{\min}) + g_i^{\min}, \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2\} \quad (20)$$

where μ_i^k is a uniformly distributed random value. \mathbf{z}_g^k and z_W^k are the measurements, and $\mathbf{v}_g^k \sim N(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{P}_g)$ and $v_W^k \sim N(0, P_W)$ are the noises.

Four different cases were examined for comparative study between the deterministic and the stochastic techniques, and Table 1 lists the parameters used to create measurements and those used to identify the constants. The measurements were created with constants $\mathbf{q}^* = [-1, 1]^T$. It is therefore expected that the techniques find constants around \mathbf{q}^* . The stochastic technique estimates constants by specifying the initial guess $\mathbf{q}^{0|0}$ and $\mathbf{P}^{0|0}$ and the covariance matrices for measurements \mathbf{P}_g and P_W (variances only).

Table 1: Parameters used to create measurements and identify the constants.

	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
\mathbf{q}^*	[-1,1]	[-1,1]	[-1,1]	[-0.75,0.75]
\mathbf{P}_g^*, P_W^*	[0,0], 0	[0.05,0.05], 0.05	[0.05,0.05], 0.05	[0.05,0.05], 0.05
\mathbf{P}_g, P_W	[10,10], 10	[10,10], 10	[10,10], 10	[10,10], 10
$\mathbf{q}^{0 0}, \mathbf{P}^{0 0}$	[-1,1], [1e10,1e10]	[-1,1], [1e10,1e10]	[-1,1], [1e-1,1e-1]	[-1,1], [1e3,1e3]

Figure 1 shows the constants identified by the deterministic and the stochastic techniques with respect to the number of steps in Case 1. The result shows that both the techniques immediately identified the exact solution. This is because measurements contain no noise, and the elastic constants are estimated from a noiseless well-defined problem.

Figure 1: Constants identified from noiseless measurements (Case 1).

Figure 2 shows the result of Case 2 with noise added to measurements. The incorrectness of the constants identified can be found for both the techniques. Similarly to the result in Case 1, the results by the two techniques are nearly identical. This indicates that there are parameters that differentiate the behaviors of the deterministic and the stochastic techniques among those which are unchanged between Cases 1 and 2.

Figure 2: Constants identified from measurements with noise (Case 2).

To first configure the mechanism of the stochastic technique to find a result equivalent to the deterministic technique, Figure 3 shows the transition of the variances and the Kalman gains. It is seen that both the variances and the Kalman gains are approaching to zero although the Kalman gains more fluctuate. The stochastic technique determines the Kalman gain such that the trace of the covariance matrix is minimized. This reduces the variances towards zero as shown in Figure 3(a), and Equation (18) gives the limit of the Kalman gain when the covariance approaches zero as

$$\lim_{\mathbf{P}^{k|k-1} \rightarrow \mathbf{0}} \mathbf{K}^k = \mathbf{0} \quad (21)$$

as Figure 3(b) demonstrates. The substitution of the decreasing Kalman gain into Equation (17) results in the estimation of a converging mean. These results are only attached to the stochastic technique. An advantage of the stochastic technique to remark is its ability to describe and quantify the certainty of the identified constants.

(a) Variances (b) Kalman gains
Figure 3: Variances and Kalman gains in Case 2.

Figure 4 shows the result of Case 3 with the prior variances each reduced to $1e-1$ from $1e10$ but with all the other parameters inheriting from Case 2. The result shows that the stochastic technique immediately finds the exact solutions whereas the constants identified by the deterministic technique fluctuate. The improvement of the stochastic result by the reduction of the prior variances indicates that the prior variances play a key role in the differentiation of the stochastic technique from the deterministic technique. With large variances, which mean that the prior knowledge is a uniform distribution, the stochastic result was identical to the deterministic one. Successful performance of the stochastic technique clearly depends on the prior knowledge.

(a) q_1 (b) q_2
Figure 4: Constants identified with small prior variances (Case 3).

Figure 5 shows the result of Case 4, which is the modification of Case 3 with each of the prior means 0.75 and each of the prior variances $1e3$. With this combination of the prior means and variances, the results of the deterministic and stochastic identification resembled. The constants identified being close to the exact solution, the efficacy of both the techniques are shown. The figure also shows the variances and the Kalman gain for the stochastic technique. Compared to Case 2, the variances require more steps for convergence due to the incorrectness of the prior knowledge.

Identification of Elastic Constants

In the identification of elastic constants, the specimen used consisted of a typical laminate composed of AS4/3506-1 laminae with a balanced $\pm 30^\circ$ stacking sequence. The anisotropic material has been reported to have the elastic constants $\mathbf{q}^* = [1.149 \cdot 10^8, 9.745 \cdot 10^6, 5.999 \cdot 10^6, 3.255 \cdot 10^6]$. Figure 6(a) shows the geometry of

the specimen as well as the loading conditions. The ungripped part of the specimen, used for identification, was of square shape with dimensions of $150\text{mm} \times 150\text{mm} \times 5\text{mm}$. A tensile test was performed where the upper surface was pulled vertically while the bottom surface was fixed both vertically and horizontally. Material tests were performed in a simulated environment. Figure 6(b) shows the points of boundary displacement/force measurements as well as elements of strain measurement. The boundary displacement/force measurements were created by specifying the loading conditions and adding artificial noises whereas the strain measurements were created by performing the two-dimensional finite element analysis with the loading conditions and adding artificial noises. As shown in the figure, 11 boundary points and 100 strain elements were measured.

Figure 5: Result of identification with different prior knowledge.

Figure 6: Experimental setting

Figure 7 shows the transitions of the elastic constants identified by the deterministic and the stochastic techniques. Although the identification of elastic constants scaled up the problem to four-dimensional space, the stochastic technique identified adequate elastic constants after taking 200 measurements. The constants identified by the deterministic technique are considerably deviated from the exact solution. The results indicate the maximum error of the stochastic technique is within 4%.

Figure 7: Elastic constant identified.

CONCLUSIONS

A generalized theoretical framework for the energy-based characterization has been presented. The framework allows both the deterministic and stochastic techniques to be described in one platform and further to be implemented for direct comparison.

The validity of the deterministic and stochastic techniques was first investigated via parametric studies with low-dimensional algebraic problems resembling the elastic identification problem. It was found that the deterministic and the stochastic techniques behave similarly when the prior variances of the stochastic technique were large and that the stochastic technique outperforms when its prior knowledge is known correctly. The techniques were finally applied to the identification of elastic constants of a composite specimen, and the results show successful identification of four elastic constants using the stochastic technique and have demonstrated its applicability to the characterization of anisotropic materials.

The work presented in this paper is a first step to the stochastic characterization of anisotropic materials and can be extended in a variety of ways. One indispensable step is the characterization of nonlinear behavior, which allows the proposed technique to be usable and useful to the prediction of damage behavior.

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